

Research Questionnaire

Delphi Study – Round One

Project: Interpersonal Conflict among Diverse Mappers in Spatial Data Co-Production

Ms. Youjin Choe, PhD Candidate

Department of Infrastructure Engineering, Faculty of Engineering
University of Melbourne

Email: ychoe@student.unimelb.edu.au

Supervisors: A/Prof. Mohsen Kalantari, Dr. Martin Tomko

Introduction

This questionnaire is the first-round survey of three with two sections: Section A with personal information and Section B with four open-ended questions. It attempts to understand disagreements among OSM users and how to resolve them. Please respond to each question in details as much as possible. The results of this round's questionnaire will be shared back to you in a brief report for further discussion in the second and third rounds.

Instruction

Please answer each of the following four questions in the next page. These four questions are designed to gather a pool of 1) conflict types, 2) factors leading to conflicts, 3) effect of conflicts, and 4) potential conflict resolution methods. Please do not hesitate to explain your answer in as much detail as possible (maximum 400 words for each question), based on your experience and knowledge in working with diverse contributors in OSM.

Please kindly return the completed questionnaire and return it to ychoe@student.unimelb.edu.au.

Your participation to this research is much appreciated.

Words used in the questions

Mappers are registered OSM users (e.g, individual volunteers, government agencies, corporate mapping teams, students, international organisations) who participate in any relevant activities.

Conflict is a disagreement among contributors on any relevant activities in OSM.

Section A

Name	
Age range (please mark "X")	Under 18
	18 to 20
	21 to 30
	31 to 40
	41 to 50
	51 to 60
	Over 60
Affiliation (please mark "X")	Volunteering individual
	Corporation (Please specify:)
	Government agency (Please specify:)
	Non-governmental organisation (Please specify:)
	Others (Please specify:)
Geographic scope of interest (for mapping)	

Section B

1. Please describe your knowledge on topics of conflict amongst mappers in OSM. (maximum 400 words)

Your answer:

2. What factors do you think that led to these conflicts? (maximum 400 words)

Your answer:

3. What are the effects of conflicts on OSM and the mappers? (maximum 400 words)

Your answer:

4. How do you think you and other mappers could resolve these conflicts? (maximum 400 words)

Your answer: